

Marketing Communication Strategy to Strengthen Brand Awareness: Case of K Commerce in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This research outlines a strategy for increasing K Commerce's awareness of the brand in Indonesia's competitive eCommerce landscape, specifically in the Jabodetabek region. An integrated marketing communication approach combining segmentation, targeting, positioning, values laddering, and the PDB triangle is offered using Kotler's STP model and differentiation concept. The findings of the study highlight a positioning and differentiation approach based on customer centricity, trust, innovation, and enjoyment. The importance of optimal content, context, and infrastructure is emphasized. Proposed taglines capture K Commerce's brand spirit, and the marketing communication strategy devised plans to overcome the awareness-appeal gap, placing K Commerce as a top brand choice among Millennials and Generation Z. This research will be used to improve K Commerce's awareness and position in eCommerce.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Content Marketing, eCommerce, Marketing Communication, Marketing Strategy

INTRODUCTION

eCommerce and social media, two critical components of our modern digital lives, have combined transformed the way people shop and stay connected. eCommerce offers a quick and diverse purchasing experience, increasing income for businesses while saving consumers time, energy, and money. At the same time, social media has transformed communication, allowing people to stay connected, establish their personal brands, and gain knowledge at an unprecedented rate.

Taking advantage of these technological advancements, forward-thinking businesses have linked eCommerce with social media, giving rise to phenomena such as social commerce and live streaming commerce. This convergence not only brings entertainment and purchasing together on a single platform, but it also allows sellers to engage consumers more effectively, presenting a dynamic, efficient, and effective solution to meet the requirements of consumers and businesses alike.

The rapid growth of social media users in Indonesia has led to the creation of social commerce, a novel kind of eCommerce that uses social technologies to create a dynamic online marketplace. Social commerce has rapidly gained popularity in the country, with around 167 million active social media users, notably among Millennials and Gen Z, who dominate social media usage. As a result of its big, tech-savvy consumers and ongoing engagement with social media platforms, Indonesia provides an ideal atmosphere for the expansion of social commerce.

K Commerce is a one-of-a-kind blend of eCommerce and social media, demonstrating the concept of social commerce with advanced algorithms that promote businesses while entertaining consumers. This platform promotes online sales by allowing users to register as sellers, which contributes to the rapid expansion of online commerce. K Commerce shows the dynamic potential and interactive nature of social commerce with varied selling tactics such as live streaming, short video content creation, and affiliate marketing.

K Commerce has evolved over the course of two years, attracting a wide range of sellers ranging from small enterprises to big brands, consolidating its place in the e-commerce industry. Despite its expansion, leading platforms like Tokopedia and Shopee continue to dominate customers' top-of-mind awareness for online buying, indicating a competitive market, as preliminary research including Millennials and Gen Z respondents showed.

The purpose of this research is to identify the PDB (Positioning-Differentiation-Brand) triangle of K Commerce in Indonesia and identify the most suitable marketing communication strategy which focuses on message, content, media, time plan, and budget for K

Commerce to be at the top of mind of consumers. The research questions of this research have three outline questions as the focuses, they are positioning, differentiation, and marketing communication.

The results of this research are limited to a specific and detailed scope in order to obtain more precise outcomes:

1. This research is limited to the Jabodetabek region with case study on Millennials and Gen Z.
2. The formulating strategy is designed to be the top of mind brand of consumer.
3. The competitors that will be compared with K Commerce are limited to two big competitors in customer's top of mind.
4. The strategy has a purpose to brand awareness only, without expecting the sales result.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The STP (Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning) concept has been extensively driven by Philip Kotler, an internationally recognized marketing professor, emphasizing that it should aspire beyond mere market division to reveal fundamental consumer wants and preferences. His segmentation theory, which groups customers based on geographic, demographic, psychographic, and behavioral categories, assists marketers in tailoring their strategies to best line with consumer desires. As a result, Kotler's ideas continue to assist marketers in improving their techniques and providing value by effectively understanding and meeting consumer expectations (Kotler & Keller, 2016). He also emphasizes the importance of positioning in developing a compelling, unique brand image that aligns with consumer needs and desires, which necessitates the development of a distinct value proposition, a strong brand persona, and clear messaging that expresses the product's or service's advantages and strengths.

Kartajaya (2017) concept of differentiation emphasizes the three primary dimensions: content, context, and infrastructure. Content differentiates through unique product offerings and brand messages, while context creates distinct customer experiences by tailoring products to specific circumstances and innovative delivery methods. The infrastructure, on the other hand, differentiates by enhancing operational processes, customer service, and the use of advanced technology, thereby creating an efficient, unique, and compelling offer that successfully appeals to customers.

Brand awareness, an important component of brand equity, refers to the amount to which consumers are familiar with and recognize a brand's qualities such as its name, logo, or other elements. It steers buying decisions by differentiating a brand from its competitors and requires the use of effective marketing methods such as advertising and public relations to increase the brand's visibility and exposure (Aaker, 1996).

One of the research objectives is to define the PDB Triangle of K Commerce. The PDB Triangle concept emphasizes the interaction of positioning, differentiation, and branding, with positioning establishing the brand's unique standing in the minds of consumers through recognizing target market demands. According to Kartajaya's concept, differentiation entails highlighting unique selling propositions to carve out a distinct identity for a brand or product and set it apart from competitors. Meanwhile, branding creates a powerful brand identity through unique names, logos, and designs, building customer loyalty and deep emotional connections, confirming the necessity of these processes in developing a successful business strategy (Kartajaya, 2005).

Kotler (2016) established the Five A's model, which describes the five important stages a buyer goes through before making a purchase: Awareness, Appeal, Ask, Act, and Advocate. This process helps firms develop effective marketing strategies, improve consumer experiences, and cultivate brand loyalty. A thorough understanding and execution of this approach may result in higher customer lifetime value, boosting the overall brand reputation and market placement. This research will focus on filling the gap between Awareness and Appeal, by increasing the brand awareness of K commerce to fight the position to be at least the three-strong position in customer's mind.

Marketing communications, which serve as crucial for facilitating communication of information between organizations and customers, have grown in importance as information technology has advanced and audiences have fragmented (Keller, 2001; Schultz, 1999). The growth of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC), a system that integrates many communication choices to create more tailored and coordinated tactics (Schultz et al., 1993; Deighton, 1996), has come from a shifting landscape.

Brands utilize social media platforms and high-quality content marketing to engage consumers, build long-term relationships, and enhance revenue by sharing important insights on a regular basis (Content Marketing Institute, 2015). The Content Marketing Matrix, which was most likely shaped by Dr. Dave Chaffey of Smart Insights, is a useful tool for evaluating current content and guiding future

plans. By categorizing information into categories aimed to entertain, inspire, educate, and persuade, a strategic method to communicate with target markets is enabled.

Brand awareness also plays an important role in influencing the purchase intention as explained by some previous research. Brand awareness refers to the level of consumer recognition and knowledge regarding a specific brand and its products. It is crucial for companies to effectively communicate information about their brand and offerings to attract potential consumers. Utilizing social media for brand awareness is particularly impactful as it can influence consumer buying behavior and contribute to increased market share. Brands should employ various strategies to keep their target audience engaged, such as sharing updates in the form of images, videos, or articles. The content should be captivating and compelling to capture readers' interest (Ansari et al.,2019). Malik et al., (2013) also conducted a research about the importance of brand awareness and brand loyalty in assessing purchase intentions of consumers with main findings that there is a robust positive correlation between brand awareness, brand loyalty, and purchase intention. When a brand has high awareness, it becomes the top-of-mind choice for customers when they intend to make a purchase, whether it be for a product or service.

The research is conducted first by identifying the segmentation and targeting of users which the result will be used to formulate the PDB Triangle. After PDB Triangle is formulated, we can know the right positioning and what kind of differentiation K Commerce must do in order to win over competitors. It generates the tagline or core messages which next will be communicated with marketing communication strategy and focus on content, media, time plan, and budget. After that there will be an implementation plan and agency brief to execute the strategy with the expected result to increase the brand awareness of K Commerce over competitors. Here is the conceptual framework of this research:

Fig I. Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The research design includes various elements such as the research question, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques. The researcher can use primary data, which is collected specifically for the research project, or secondary data, which has been collected previously for another purpose. In this way, research design plays a crucial role in ensuring that the research study is conducted efficiently, effectively, and ethically.

Fig II. Research Design

B. Data Collection Methods

The author uses the primary data by conducting online surveys and secondary data by collecting data from previous research, and business or marketing agencies. The questionnaires structures divided into six parts : screening, to screen and understand the respondent profile, segmentation, targeting, values laddering, and positioning-differentiation-branding to analyze respondent’s response for two top tier eCommerce and K Commerce current marketing position, and marketing communication initiatives to dig more respondent’s response toward existing marketing communication of two top tier eCommerce and K Commerce. The respondent will be focused on Millennials and Gen Z respondents who domiciled in Jabodetabek, active in media social and have ever purchased something in eCommerce.

C. Data Analysis Methods

After data collected from respondents, the researcher will do the validity and reliability test. Validity and reliability are two important concepts in research that assess the quality and credibility of research findings. Validity refers to the degree to which a research study measures what it is intended to measure, while reliability refers to the consistency and stability of the results obtained from a research study. Then the researcher will make an analysis related to the current position of K Commerce and competitors by looking for the percentage of the data collected. After that, the researcher will formulate the marketing communication strategy by analyzing the data

related to segmentation-targeting-positioning, values laddering, and positioning-differentiation-branding triangle into marketing plan, implementation plan, and agency brief.

FINDINGS, ANALYSIS AND BUSINESS SOLUTION

Questionnaire was distributed with 110 respondents, with screening items such as born in 1981-2012, domiciled in Jabodetabek, having social media account, have ever shopped in Shopee/Tokopedia/K Commerce, have shopped in Shopee or Tokopedia in last three months, and have a TikTok account. For 110 respondents who actively shop in eCommerce and already installed the TikTok application in their phone, 30% of them have shopped at K Commerce, and as 70% never shop at K Commerce. Shopee and Tokopedia are still excelling at the top of mind of customers.

Author makes a comprehensive analysis of segmenting, targeting, positioning, and differentiation based on the questionnaire that is related to each aspect. Besides that, the author also makes the analysis of marketing communication initiatives to know the perspective of respondents about the way marketing content is delivered to customers. From the analysis, the author can formulate the business solution such as positioning strategy, differentiation strategy, PDB triangle, and marketing communication strategy.

A. Positioning Strategy

Positioning terms will be known by formulating the value proposition and reason to believe. Value proposition will be determined by using values laddering as a tool. Values laddering is composed of three primary components, there are product attributes, functional benefits or consequential benefits, and emotional benefits or personal values. By those three essentials, it can create the value proposition of K Commerce. From formulating the values laddering, there are three value propositions that may be applied by K Commerce. They are customer centricity, trustworthiness, and innovation and enjoyment.

Reason to Believe (RTB) is a hands-on idea that finds frequent application in marketing and advertising, as opposed to being an academic model or theory that might usually feature in research papers. Nevertheless, the roots of RTB can be traced back to scholarly theories like the "Source Credibility Theory", put forward by Hovland, Janis, and Kelley in 1953, and the "Elaboration Likelihood Model", introduced by Petty and Cacioppo in 1986. According to the analysis of positioning, the author makes three summaries for the reason to believe for K Commerce, they are quality assurance, secure transactions, and exceptional value.

B. Differentiation Strategy

Differentiation strategy will be focused on content, context, and features-infrastructure of K Commerce. Based on the analysis from differentiation aspect, the author formulates the differentiation strategy as below:

Table I. Differentiation Strategy

Differentiation		
Content	Context	Infrastructure
Product Selection and Quality	Augmented Reality Integration	Interface (Social Shopping Interface, AR-Enabled Product Visualization, Personalized Interface Themes, AI-Based Assistant)
Engaging Promotional Ads	Community-Driven Shopping Experience	Delivery (Green Delivery Option, Scheduled Delivery, Local Pickup Points)
Gamification	Personalized Shopping Journeys	Payment (Buy Now, Pay Later, Split Payment Options, Secure Biometric Payment)

		Service (In-app Customer Service Chat, In-app Tailoring Services)
		Return (Hassle-free Return Policy, Returns at Local Stores)

C. PDB Triangle

The PDB triangle of K Commerce would be built upon the positioning pillars of customer centricity, trustworthy and secure eCommerce, and good value of sellers and products, which are then expressed through differentiated content, context, and infrastructure, ultimately creating a brand that is innovative, reliable, and engaging.

Fig III. PDB Strategy of K Commerce

D. Tagline

Based on PDB Triangle of K Commerce and also target persona, there are five recommendations of Tagline for K Commerce from author

- A Unique and Wonderful Shopping Experience
- More Than Shopping, Truly Exciting!
- Show Your Creativity and Personality

- The Next Level of Shopping
- Find a Different Shopping Experience!

E. Marketing Communication Strategy

Marketing communication strategy in this research will be focused on four aspects, content, media, time, and budget.

Content that Can be Used in K Commerce

Connecting the 5A of the customer path with the K Commerce situation, the author decides the content will be focused on filling the gap between awareness and appeal. The suitable contents for this path are entertaining and educational. The examples for entertaining purposes are influencer challenges, interactive games, behind the scenes, and discount and giveaway information. The examples for educational purposes are infographics, product demos, tips and tricks, and publishing insightful articles.

Suggested Media to Deliver Content

According to the marketing communication aspect analysis, customers used to see the advertisement in social media. Nowadays social media is closer to their daily life than other media (television, radio, print media, and billboards) because it can be accessed by phone which is more handy. But the author still suggests using offline advertisements such as billboards and offline events as a media to deliver more awareness, if business has more budget in marketing. Besides optimizing the content in both media, K Commerce may use paid advertising in social media.

Suggested Time to Deliver Content

Each content form has different media to deliver the contents. So does in time of delivering. Each content has its own unique peak time, so it is better to customize the timing of content to get optimal results. Author tries to formulate the general suggested time to deliver the content based on the analysis of the marketing communication aspect, target persona, and also best practices.

Suggested Budget to Deliver Content

For the budget strategy, the author chose the Objective and Task Method from IMC as outlined by Belch (2019) to formulate the marketing budget plan. Objective and task method is a method which identifies the precise marketing objectives and tasks that need to be accomplished, followed by estimating the cost associated with each task. This approach offers a comprehensive breakdown of the budget allocation, ensuring that the objectives outlined in the marketing plan are in line with the suggestion budget.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions

1. Current positioning of the K Commerce is still below rather than Shopee and Tokopedia in brand awareness aspect.
2. From positioning analysis, there are three key points that can be highlighted to be applied to K Commerce: customer-centricity, trustworthy and secure eCommerce, and good value of sellers and products
3. From differentiation analysis, there are three key points that can be highlighted to be applied to K Commerce: interactive shopping experience, extensive community integration, and personalized and convenient services
4. For marketing communication strategy, content will be focused on entertaining and educational purpose, can be delivered both in online and offline media (adapt to the right type of content), the timing will follow the type of media that the content will be delivered at, and for the budget, will be adapt with the given budget and also adapt with the type of content, the media to deliver content, the stakeholders, and the frequency of the contents are delivered.

B. Recommendations

Based on findings, analysis, and business solutions, the author suggests the following activities to fix the problems:

1. Product enhancement: In order to differentiate K Commerce from competitors, K Commerce must be outstanding, special, and differentiated from others. Author already makes some recommendations toward the product enhancement. The marketing communication will not be optimal without the upgrading of the products of K Commerce.
2. Executing the marketing communication strategy: Parallel with the product enhancement, K Commerce may execute the strategy by creating the timeline and working together with third parties or agencies. Below is the recommendation of agency brief:

Table II. Agency Brief

AGENCY BRIEF PLAN FOR PRODUCT DEMO BIM 7-8 K COMMERCE
PROJECT NAME
Product Demo Youtube Bi Month 7-8, 2023
Objectives
<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The goal of this campaign is to raise brand awareness of K Commerce and the platform's products, with a focus on demonstrating both their functionality and their quality.- This also aims to assist potential customers in making educated purchasing choices, drive sales for K Commerce and its sellers, and establish K Commerce as a trustworthy marketplace for high-quality products.
Target Audience
Millennials and Generation Z customers who use social media and are likely to make online purchases.
Key Message
K Commerce is a dependable and accessible marketplace with a large range of high-quality products. It aims to demonstrate the worth and functionality of these products in order to encourage potential customers to shop at K Commerce.
Style and Tone
The style of the content will be informative and engaging. To attract viewers, it will use storytelling and interactive content. The tone will be casual and friendly making the content feel comfortable and relatable to the target audience. To develop trust with the audience, it should appear natural and honest, rather than overtly promotional.
Project Timeline
The content must be uploaded to Youtube in the first week of July. The shooting process and final editing must be finished 3 days before the content broadcast date.
Budget
Rp 20.000.000,-

Deliverables and Format

The deliverables will be bi-monthly product demo videos, each about 10-15 minutes long and demonstrating a different product category. The product selection for this bi-month is home living products. The videos will be created in high-definition format for release on YouTube and other social media sites. They will include an influencer and a seller discussing and showing the product, such as unboxing, going over its features, demonstrating how it works, and emphasizing its advantages. With clear branding, compelling imagery, and strong calls to action, the content will be maximized for sharing.

3. Maintaining the operational, timeline, and budget while the execution process
4. Review and get feedback from stakeholders and customers related to the marketing communications that had been executed
5. Suggestion for further research: enlarge the respondents to get larger insight and deeper research scope. Besides that, do the evaluation at least once a month to tactical monitoring and evaluation.

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